

High-frequency electric current welding with suprachoroidal approach to treat retinal detachment: timing of morphological changes and strength of chorioretinal adhesion

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Purpose

Chorioretinal adhesions (CRA) are essential in retinal detachment surgery. To evaluate the morphological changes (MC) and CRA strength (CRAS), a high-frequency electric current welding (HFECW) was applied with suprachoroidal approach on experimental animal model to cause CRA.

Methods

For HFECW, a modified generator EK-300M1 (E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute, Kyiv, Ukraine) with pre-settings (66 kHz, three groups: 10-12 Volts (V), 12-14 V and 14-16 V) was used. Treated eyes were enucleated in 1 hour (h), 3, 7, 14 and 30 days after treatment. A study of the MC of the CRA was performed on 54 (108 eyes) adult chinchilla rabbits (32 eyes per group, 12 control eyes); the retina was treated 7-10 mm posterior to the limbus through a U-shaped scleral incision with suprachoroidal approach using 25-gauge tip (treated area diameter/size 0.260 mm/0.053 mm²). The eyes were analyzed using H&E staining and light microscopy. Study of CRAS was performed on 52 (104 eyes) rabbits: (32 eyes per group, 8 control eyes). CRAS was measured using a biomechanical force elongation tester. The reduction in weight at the time of CRA rupture was registered as a measure for adhesion strength.

Results

The MC showed an instant increase in the CRA in the area of HFECW application, which further strengthened with time. The retina responded by apparent destruction of rods, cones, loss of bipolar, amacrine, horizontal and ganglion cells, development of cysts and migration of RPEs, while the choroid showed damage and migration of melanocytes. By day 30, a partial cell regeneration and connective tissue degeneration was noticed. Adjacent retina remained intact. The study of CRAS showed that after application of 10-12 V at 1 h from treatment with HFECW a CRAS was 8.75% and 25.74% higher than that of 12-14 V and 14-16 V, respectively, and at 1 week it was 10.18% and 9.54% higher than that of 12-14 V and 14-16 V, respectively.

Conclusions

Application of HFECW with suprachoroidal approach can induce an instant CRA, which strengthens within first weeks from surgery. Application of lower force (10-12 V) showed a higher CRA strength. HFECW with suprachoroidal approach could be an alternative method to treat retinal tears, reducing the need for endotamponade and vitreoretinal surgery.

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Session: [Retina Cell Biology](#)

Thu, Apr 27, 2023

12:45pm - 2:30pm (Central)

Poster Range: B0179 - B0209

Moderators: Wei Liu (Albert Einstein College of Med), Diana M Mitchell (University of Idaho)

Session Types

Poster Session

Section

Retinal Cell Biology

Presentations		
Poster Session	B0179: Low-dose efavirenz rescues retinal function and decreases intraocular pressure in Apoj ^{-/-} mice 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Nicole EL-Darzi
Poster Session	B0180: The role of Lipe in lipid metabolism in the retina 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Seher Yuksel
Poster Session	B0181: Pharmacological reduction of ceramides increases levels of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids in the mouse retina 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Dominik Lewandowski
Poster Session	B0182: VLC-PUFA supplementation increases Elovanoic acid synthesis in a two-compartment Late-Onset Retinal Degeneration-iRPE ... 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Jeff Xiang Ji
Poster Session	B0183: Functional analysis of the ciliary protein transport regulating kinase ICK in retinal photoreceptor cells 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Yamato Maeda
Poster Session	B0184: Changes in Retinal Cell Populations after Treatment with an $\alpha 7$ Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptor Agonist by Flow Cytometry 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Hope Vanzo-Sparks
Poster Session	B0185: Participation of the TRPV4 channel in basal and evoked retinal function in a mouse model of obesity induced by cafeteria diet 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Cynthia Alejandra Rodríguez Arzate
Poster Session	B0186: High-frequency electric current welding with suprachoroidal approach to treat retinal detachment: timing of morphological c... 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Lyubomyr Lytvynchuk
Poster Session	B0187: Evaluating the reliability of Brn3a and RBPMS as markers of retinal ganglion cells with age and ocular hypertension-induce... 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Miranda Meng
Poster Session	B0188: Characteristics of retinal ganglion cell (RGC) degeneration with age and cuprizone-induced model of multiple sclerosis (CP... 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Soyoung Choi
Poster Session	B0189: The influence of microfluidics on retinal ganglion cell neurite outgrowth 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Celine Tater
Poster Session	B0190: Rho-kinase involvement in ocular fibrosis 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Yuebing Li
Poster Session	B0191: Multiomic characterization of mouse retinal aging 12:45pm-2:30pm Apr 27 (Central)	 Isabella Palazzo

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